

From Traditional Ranking System To Transfer Of Knowledge Based Ranking Index: Introducing A Fully Automated Transfer Of Knowledge Ranking Index For Higher Educational Institutions

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 18, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Transfer of Knowledge, Transfer of knowledge-based Ranking Index, HEIs Ranking System, and Higher Education Institutions</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5527137</p>	<p><i>Purpose: The study is built on the premise that the prevailing higher educational institutions (HEIs) ranking systems fail to measure the knowledge management activities in general and transfer of knowledge (ToK) activities in particular in HEIs. The study advocates the adaptation of the right measurement technique aligned with the mission of HEIs which is the creation and transfer of knowledge. The study presents a new ranking index based on transfer of knowledge that divides HEIs into High, Medium, and Low ToK categories. Study design/methodology/approach: The ToK ranking index is based on learnings from transfer of knowledge and university ranking works of literature and for index development process protocols developed by Paul E. Spector (1992), Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) handbook on Constructing Composite Indicators (2008), Earl R. Babbie (2012), Robert F. Devellis, (2012) and Ashley Crossman (2019) were reviewed. The study has also kept the use of technology in view for data-driven decision-making in HEI and has developed a fully automated version of the ToK ranking Index.</i></p> <p><i>Findings: The ToK ranking index consists of seven dimensions subsequently divided into 86 items. A pilot test was carried out to establish the validity of the instrument. Originality/value: The study identifies the gap in HEIs ranking systems and the expected performance from HEIs in the new knowledge economy and takes a step further by developing a new ToK based ranking system, which will assist in mapping and measuring the HEIs activities in the context of ToK.</i></p>

Introduction

University ranking is an interesting and appealing area with multiple benefits, e.g. helps students in choosing an institution for higher education, helps governments in the provision of funding, helps researchers in carrying out new research insights in the top ranking universities and even helps the (ranked) universities to become a part of healthy competition. However, several reviews (e.g. Anowar et al., 2015; Henk F. Moed, 2017; Vernon, Balas & Momani, 2018) about university ranking systems have highlighted issues of inter-correlation between factors, the validity of factors, overlapping factors and skewness of indicator distributions, etc. The reviews suggested that the indicators used in ranking the universities are to some extent confined into some traditional ideas and require the inclusion of more up-to-date indicators, measuring the new knowledge economy led roles of HEI. The shift from an industrial economy to a knowledge economy has undoubtedly put the HEIs under pressure; with governments demanding more usable knowledge with cost efficiency, industry demanding readily available knowledge products, innovation and internationalization pushing HEIs for a more market-linked curriculum (Levine, 2006). Regardless of the given factual argument, knowledge transfer in Higher Educational Institutions (HEI) is not a new concept as HEIs exist to create and disseminate knowledge, what's new is the institutionalization of university-industry linkage. Wedgewood (2006) called this new reality as "mainstreaming the third stream", which demands significant engagement from academics. Wedgewood (2006) argued that universities cannot survive based on teaching and research, they have to collaborate with the third sector for creating meaningful social and economic impact. HEI should transfer knowledge not only for creating income by generating patents and licenses but also for developing meaningful academic collaborations with non-profit organizations, government and other organizations for developing strategically efficient improvements in partner organizations (Reichenfeld, 2011). Thus, in its new role, HEI ranking needs to be based on HEI transfer of knowledge capacity i-e how much knowledge created inside the

HEI is transferred to the outside world using various means like research, accessibility and networking etc. (Holi & Wickramasinghe, 2008).

1.1. Rational for a Transfer of Knowledge-Based Ranking System

Several HEI in the world are measuring their transfer of knowledge output and outcome, through a set of pre-defined transfer of knowledge activities undertaken by HEI (Holi & Wickramasinghe, 2008). For example Association of University Technology Managers (AUTM) collects data through an annual licensing survey (Bostrom & Flanagan, 2003), Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) in collaboration with Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA) measures the transfer of knowledge activities of HEI for funding decision and Scottish Funding Council (SFC) for its transfer of knowledge activities. Apart from HEI, other organizations in UK e.g. UNICO (The University Companies Association) developed metrics for the assessment of transfer of knowledge activities. Yet there are no specific instruments that measure the transfer of knowledge because KT is heavily impacted by the types of knowledge. Especially tacit knowledge can be exceptionally difficult to measure as it is embedded in the individual mind such as ideas, skills, and experience. Several approaches are used in measuring the transfer of knowledge e.g. Argote and Ingram, (2000) measured knowledge transfer (KT) from the changes on the recipient side; (i) changes in their performance (ii) the induced changes of the recipient's knowledge-base (iii) changes in cumulative knowledge that resides in various repositories. KT is also measured by the process and outcome dimensions. The outcome dimension measures transfer of knowledge from the financial and non-financial criteria. The financial criteria measures KT by the stakeholder's equity, cost reduction, number of patents or intellectual property owned (e.g. Perez-Nordtvedt et al., 2008; Lichtenthaler, 2010) and for non-financial criteria, some researchers have measured KT from the amount of successful KT engagements during any period (Li & Hsieh, 2009), slight changes in the learning-by-doing knowledge level (Cha et al., 2008) and the frequency of contact with knowledge source (Kang et al., 2010) The process dimension usually divide the KT process into various stages; Initiation, Implementation, Ramp-up and Integration (Szulanski, 2000); Motivation, Match, Implementation and Retentive (Kwan & Cheung, 2006); Search and Transfer (Hansen, 1999) and Socialization, Externalization, Internalization and Combination (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995). A process view of KT allows a critical examination of how difficulty evolves over stages of the transfer. It can also provide important insight into the working of various organizational arrangements to transfer knowledge, communicate managerial interventions and help design and implement mechanisms that support effective transfer of knowledge. Researchers have also measured KT from the perspective of learning capabilities or learning performance (i.e. the speed, type, extent, and nature of the "new knowledge learned" (Martinkenaite, 2011). Out of the approaches used to measure the transfer of knowledge, past researchers have predominantly measured KT from the outcome perspectives as it is tangible with detailed supporting data and largely in documented form as compared to process perspectives.

1.2. Transfer of knowledge Ranking System- The context of Pakistan

Higher Education Institutions (HEI) of Pakistan are operating in a highly dynamic environment and are exposed to challenges that have accrued because of structural changes in managing higher education in the country. Some critical reforms made in the sector since 2002 include the evolution of the Higher education commission (HEC). HEC is the primary autonomous regulatory body of higher education, realigning education and skills to Pakistan's socioeconomic objectives, training of faculty members abroad, opening up of new HEI, and physical infrastructure improvements. The objective of the Commission is to transform the economy into a knowledge- and services-based economy by creating international centers of research and innovation.

An overall assessment of the Pakistani higher education sector against the set targets of Medium Term Development Framework-II (MDTF-II) was conducted by Dr. Khalid Mahmood (2016). The assessment concluded that HEC has weak evaluation systems which hinder HEC's capacity of tracking the progress and performance of HEI. HEC has developed three evaluation criteria for ranking HEI (public and private) in Pakistan. The used ranking criteria focused on multiple dimensions in a single instance i-e implementation of regulations, capacity building of faculty, student-teacher ratio, research publication and grants. Mahmood's (2016) report recommended that financial grants provision to HEI by HEC should be subject to achievement of certain targets, these targets can be outlined in HEC evaluation of HEI through a comprehensive evaluation index. The recommendation of developing a comprehensive tool that can evaluate HEI on indicators like number of graduates, number of enrollment in a year, research publications and projects, etc. was advised in the presence of several HEC ranking criteria for HEI.

The need of introducing a new ranking system along with the need to redefine the Pakistani HEIs role in the knowledge economy was further strengthened when HEC announced its vision 2025 in 2017 (aligned with the Government of Pakistan's vision 2025) (<https://www.hec.gov.pk/>). HEC 2025 vision considers HEI as a learning center for transformation into a knowledge economy. The knowledge economy is defined as an economy that considers knowledge as its currency, an economy that is based on creation (production), transfer/dissemination and application of knowledge for creating goods and services (Dunning, 2000; Powell & Snellman 2004; Gerhardt,

2019). Thus, if HEIs in Pakistan are going to be centers of transformation in the knowledge economy, they have to adapt to new entrepreneurial or service-oriented roles (explained in the literature review) compared to traditional teaching and research roles.

The ToK ranking index development process was divided into two parts; part-I covers the index development and part-II is about the automation of the ToK ranking index. Both the parts are explained in the subsequent discussion.

Figure-1: Components of Transfer of Knowledge Index Development

PART-1

2. Transfer of knowledge Ranking Index Development Process

For developing the transfer of knowledge index the work of Paul E. Spector (1992), Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) handbook on Constructing Composite Indicators (2008), Earl R. Babbie (2012), Robert F. Devellis, (2012) and Ashley Crossman (2019) was reviewed. The steps outlined in the mentioned sources were combined to develop the following framework for developing the ToK index:

Figure-2 Transfer of Knowledge Index Development Process (source: Adapted from Spector (1992). OECD-2018, Babbie (2012), Devellis (2012) and Crossman (2019))

2.1. Dimensions Selection and Definitions

The proposed ToK ranking index was found to be largely dependent on two sets of literature; transfer of knowledge literature, a sub-part of knowledge management literature, and university ranking literature. For dimensions selection and definition both were reviewed. The theoretical definitions of terms e.g. “transfer of knowledge”, “networking”, “transfer of knowledge processes” etc. were adapted from the transfer of knowledge literature. Whereas, dimensions to be used for operationalization of ToK were mainly extracted from university ranking literature, full filing the theoretical definition of transfer of knowledge i-e. the actual movement of knowledge within and among people (individual/group) and within and among entities (unit/department). Table-2 provides an overview of the common themes extracted from literature, highlighting the dimensions and sub-dimensions for a probable operationalization of transfer of knowledge at the higher educational institutional level.

Table-1: Common Transfer of Knowledge Dimensions for HEI

Dimensions	Sub-Dimensions	Source
Research/ Research Support/ Research Commercialization	Collaborative Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Association of University Technology Managers (AUTM) ● Composite Indicator for Knowledge Transfer by Finne et al., (2010) commissioned by the European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation ● HEC-Pakistan Performance Matrix for Office of Research Innovation and
	Commercialization of research	
	Consultancy	
	Contract Research	
	Institutional co-operation in R&D and other phases of innovation	
Human Transfer	Knowledge transfer through	

Activities	trained people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commercialization (ORIC) (2018) HEC-ranking criteria (2010-2015) Higher Education Funding Council for England developed and run a systematic Higher Education – Business and Community Interaction Survey (HE-BCI). Metrics for the Evaluation of Transfer of Knowledge at Universities by Holi and Wickramasinghe (2008), commissioned by Universities Companies Association (UNICO), UK trade association for technology transfer QS star methodology (2013-2018)
	Continuing Professional Development (CPD)	
Entrepreneurial Activities	Institutional support for entrepreneurship & economic development	
	Value Creation Activities	
Intellectual Property Activities	Patents	
	Licensing	
	Technology Knowledge Transfer Activities	
Academic Activities/ Teaching Quality	Teaching	
	Graduates to industry	
Finance and Facilities/ Capacity Building	Training	
	Accesses to Knowledge repositories	
Community and Cultural Activities/ Social Integration	Networks	

Seven dimensions are most commonly used to measure the transfer of knowledge activity in an HEI. These dimensions are most closely linked with the mission of HEIs i.e creation and transfer of knowledge. As evident from table-2, the given dimensions are mostly the primary activities that HEIs perform e.g. academic activities, activities based on or related to research and/or commercialization of research (e.g. research publications, patent filing, licensing, funded research projects), capacity building of faculty and staff, developing relationships with community for social integration, etc. thus, as a first step common dimensions used in literature were extracted.

Once the common dimensions for ToK Ranking Index were shortlisted, a comprehensive list of used sources was developed. The list of sources not only identified the source but also the dimension and or sub-dimension shortlisted from a particular source. Table-3 provides an overview as follows:

Table-2: Sources of ToK Index

S. No.	Source	Source Dimension	Code
1	HEC-Performance Matrices for ORIC (2018)	Research Support	HEC-ORIC-1
		Capacity Building/HR Development	HEC-ORIC-2
		Research Commercialization	HEC-ORIC-3
2	HEC-Ranking Criteria (2010-2015)	Teaching Quality	HEC-Ranking-1
		Research	HEC-Ranking-2
		Finance and Facility	HEC-Ranking-3
		Social Integration/Community Development	HEC-Ranking-4
3	QS-Star Methodology (2013-2018)	Employability	QS-Star-1
		Research	QS-Star-2
		Learning Environment	QS-Star-3
		Access	QS-Star-4
		Innovation	QS-Star-5
4	Association of University Technology Managers (AUTM) 2010	Ecosystem of institution	AUTM-1
		Human Transfer Activities	AUTM-2
		Technology Knowledge Transfer Activities	AUTM-3

5	A Composite Indicator for Knowledge Transfer by Finne et al., (2010)	Institutional co-operation in R&D and other phases of innovation	CIKT-1
		Commercialization of research	CIKT-2
6	Metrics For The Evaluation Of Knowledge Transfer Activities At Universities by Holi & Wickramasinghe (2008)	Teaching	MEKT-1
		Licensing	MEKT-2
7	The Higher Education – Business and Community Interaction Survey (HE-BCI)	Intellectual Property	HE-BCI-1

In total seven sources were utilized covering both national (Pakistan) and international literature. The sources along with a particular dimension or sub-dimension to be used (from that particular) source were recorded. The dimensions were again aligned with the already developed list of common dimensions highlighted in the literature (table-2). Using the aforementioned sources and common themes for measuring ToK, the following dimensions for measuring ToK in HEI were adapted for the study. The common ToK dimensions were rewritten to bring conformity of language and structure. The final ToK index (based on literature) consisted of seven dimensions, two dimensions (Knowledge Transfer through Research and Knowledge Transfer through value creation were divided into sub-dimensions). Table-4 provides the details as follows:

Table-3: Dimensions of the Transfer of Knowledge Index

S. No.	Dimensions	Sub-Dimensions	Source
1	Knowledge Transfer through Academic Activity	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HEC-R-1 ● MEKT-1
2	Knowledge Transfer through Research	Academic Publication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HEC-ORIC-1 ● HEC-R-2
		Research Projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● QS-Star-2
3	Knowledge Transfer through Trained People	Faculty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HEC-ORIC-2 ● HEC-R-2
		Graduates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● QS-Star-2 ● AUTM-3
4	Knowledge Transfer through Accessibility	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HEC-R-3
5	Knowledge Transfer through Networking	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● QS-Star-3 ● AUTM-1
6	Knowledge Transfer through Technology	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HEC-ORIC-3 ● CIKT-2 ● MEKT-2 ● HE-BCI-1
7	Knowledge Transfer through Value Creation	Entrepreneurship and Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HEC-R-4 ● QS-Star-5
		Community Programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AUTM-1 ● CIKT-1

Once the list of dimensions along with sub-dimensions was finalized, description/interpretations for each dimension was drafted (aligned with university ranking and transfer of knowledge literature) as follows:

Table-4: ToK Ranking Index - Dimensions Description

Dimensions	Interpretation
1. Knowledge Transfer through Academic Activity	<p>Based on the reviewed sources five academic transfer activities were selected; (1). Taught Degree Programs: Taught degree programs directly transfer knowledge from faculty (sender of knowledge) to enrolled students (recipients of knowledge). (2). New Degree Programs: Introduction of new degree programs in HEI again shows the updated transfer of knowledge from faculty to enrolled students. New degree programs also indicate the HEI market linkage. (3). Curricula Revision: Curricula revision is an important activity in academic institutions. Curricula revision directly documents and transfers faculty newly acquired or created knowledge to students. This activity is also helpful in case the HEI is not introducing a new degree program, changes in existing curricula enforces up-gradation and update (based on market demand and currently available knowledge). (4). Short Courses/Diploma Programs: Short courses and diploma programs transfer knowledge to an extended audience. In other words, the HEI transfers knowledge to an audience other than registered students and (5). Associate Degree Programs: Associate degree programs provide an opportunity for practitioners to enroll in professional degrees. Thus, such degrees also transfer knowledge from faculty to registered students.</p>
2. Knowledge Transfer through Research	<p>The second dimension of research was divided into two sub-dimensions i-e. Academic research and research projects. <u>Academic Research</u> focused on research publications of an HEI, whereas <u>Research Projects</u> took the funded research activities of an HEI into account. (1). Academic Research was divided into five activities; (i). HEI Research Journal: HEI research journals provide researchers with an opportunity to transfer the created knowledge with the academic community at large. Thus, journal/s published by HEI is considered an important transfer activity. For the study, HEC recognized journals published by HEI are included as transfer activity and are divided into three categories (as defined and categorized by HEC) i-e. W, X, Y and Z. (ii). Research Publication: Research publications directly transfer faculty created knowledge to the academic community. For the study publications in HEC recognized journals are taken into account and are divided into W, X, Y, and Z categories. (iii). Citation: A more direct measurement of transfer of knowledge is the research publication citation. Citation indicates that the transferred knowledge has not only reached the receiver but is also transferred further by the receiver. Thus, the citation of impact factor research papers was included. (iv). Books/Book Chapters: Faculty transfers knowledge via publishing books or chapters in a book. Therefore this transfer activity was also taken into the research publication dimension and (v). Conference Papers: Conference papers are yet another way of transferring knowledge from faculty to the academic community, thus, it was also taken into account. (2). Research Projects: HEI also takes part in funded research projects e.g. in Pakistan we have HEC funded projects (e.g. NRPU, SRGP etc.), research projects funded by provincial and federal govt. of Pakistan and research projects funded by international development partners (e.g. World Bank, UNDP, USAID etc.) and by industry. Through these funded research projects, knowledge is transferred from one entity (faculty and HEI) to another entity therefore these activities were included in the ToK index.</p>
3. Knowledge Transfer through Trained People	<p>An academic institution is about faculty and students (enrolled and graduated), thus transfer through people was divided into two sub-dimensions (1). Transfer of Knowledge through Faculty: Transfer through faculty members takes place when faculty members deliver or attend training, workshops and conferences. Similarly, faculty delivers invited talks and plays a vital role in editorial boards as well. Faculty members also supervise research and thus can transfer the knowledge created within the HEI. Faculty development programs are also a source of knowledge transfer. HEI along with permanent and contractual faculty members uses the services of visiting faculty members from industry and other academic institutions. The visiting faculty brings in knowledge created outside an HEI and transfers it to the students within the HEI, thus, visiting faculty members are also a source of transfer of knowledge. (2). Transfer of Knowledge through Graduates: Academic institutions transfer knowledge to the market/industry via graduates as well as through enrolled students. The number of graduates and enrolled students per year represents the transfer of knowledge activity in</p>

	<p>an academic institution as knowledge from faculty is transferred to students and through students, the knowledge is transferred directly to the industry/marketplace at large. Students during their stay at academic intuitions take part in conferences, workshops, training sessions and seminars. All these activities provide a breeding ground for the transfer of knowledge. Apart from curricular activities, students take part in co-curricular activities e.g. debate competitions, essay writing and business fares. These co-curricular activities also nourish the transfer activity and help in the actual movement of knowledge from one entity to another.</p>
4. Knowledge Transfer through Accessibility	<p>Knowledge needs to be accessible (to the receiver of knowledge) if it is to be transferred. Thus, it requires an opportunity or platform as a medium for transference. This medium is at times a conference, workshop, training, classroom or co-curricular activity setting or at times simply require access to libraries (digital and physical), where books, journals, and periodicals etc. works as a message sent by the sender of knowledge (author/researcher) which is received by the student or faculty (as receiver of knowledge). Thus, the accessibility of knowledge creates an opportunity for sending or receiving knowledge. The dimension of accessibility, though is not explicitly stated in the aforementioned literature sources yet it is measured via institutions' capacity of providing required facilities. Facilities like common rooms/shared informal discussion rooms etc. were also counted for accessibility provision by HEI. Faculty exchange their ideas (send tacit knowledge) and receive feedback (receive tacit knowledge) while spending time with other colleagues. This transfer activity assists in building up the academic and research ideas of faculty members. Thus, the provision of such meeting places is also included in the transfer of knowledge via accessibility to knowledge.</p>
5. Knowledge Transfer through Networking	<p>Academic intuitions are the centers of linkages let that be with govt., industry or other academic institutions. HEIs develop faculty and students exchange programs based on academic linkages, receive funding from govt., industry, and development partners for research projects as an output of successful industry-academia linkages. The same network is used for inviting experts to deliver talks in HEI and arrange events like job fairs etc. Thus, this network of relationships with govt., industry, academic institutions and developing partners play a vital role in transferring knowledge.</p>
6. Knowledge Transfer through Technology	<p>HEI are technology prototype development hubs. Faculty and students work on research projects that result in new product development. Similarly, HEI transfers newly created knowledge to the industry that makes use of these new insights for technology development. This dimension focuses on the HEI capacity of transferring knowledge via technological knowledge transfer. This includes the number of patents/licenses filled for or received, number of the contractual relationships that an academic institution has with companies for technology development or use. This dimension also includes the experiential learning opportunities initiated by HEI for students.</p>
7. Knowledge Transfer through Value Creation	<p>HEI creates value for society by creating self-employment training opportunities and community uplift programs. Thus Knowledge Transfer through value creation was divided into two sub-dimensions: (1). Knowledge Transfer through Entrepreneurship and Innovation: HEI train students/youth to set up their enterprises. HEI in Pakistan with HEC and govt. funding has set up incubation programs for assisting students/youth in setting up their businesses. This entrepreneurship activity creates value for society as new products and services are developed. (2). Knowledge Transfer through Community Programs: HEI also focuses on community uplift by arranging awareness seminars and donation campaigns for social causes. Both the activities result in value addition and improvement in living standards. Since, both require the movement of knowledge from one entity (faculty, HEI) to another entity (students, youth, community and nonprofit organizations), thus are included in the transfer of knowledge activity.</p>

2.2. Item Pool Development

The item pool development step started with one key question; how many items per dimension/sub-dimension? The answer was relatively easy to find as the shortlisted study sources (table-3) provided a mother list/pool of items per dimension/sub-dimension. The only task was to look for items that fulfilled the theoretical definition of transfer i-e the actual moment of knowledge. For-example in the knowledge accessibility dimension the physical infrastructure of a library doesn't indicate the transfer process, however, the number of books available in the library does indicate the transfer or moment of knowledge. Thus, the available list of items given in the seven shortlisted sources was reviewed and a final list of 86 items for the ToK ranking index was developed. The following table provides a summary of the items per dimensions and sub-dimension (sources mentioned), whereas appendix-I Provides a comprehensive detail of the selected items.

Table-5: Transfer of Knowledge Index – Item List

Dimensions	Sub-Dimensions	Sub-Item No.	Total Item No.	Source
1. KT through Academic Activity	None	5	5	● HEC-R-1 ● MEKT-1
2. KT through Research	Academic Publication	13	17	● HEC-ORIC-1 ● HEC-R-2 ● QS-Star-2
	Research Projects	4		
3. KT through Trained People	Faculty	11	21	● HEC-ORIC-2 ● HEC-R-2 ● QS-Star-2 ● AUTM-3
	Graduates	10		
4. KT through Accessibility	None	8	8	● HEC-R-3
5. KT through Networking	None	13	13	● QS-Star-3 ● AUTM-1
6. KT through Technology	None	8	8	● HEC-ORIC-3 ● CIKT-2 ● MEKT-2 ● HE-BCI-1
7. KT through Value Creation	Entrepreneurship and Innovation	11	14	● HEC-R-4 ● QS-Star-5 ● AUTM-1 ● CIKT-1
	Community Programs	3		
Total			86	

2.3. Weightage Assignment

The following step-wise process was followed for assigning weights:

Figure-3: Weightage Assignment Steps

The sources used for the development of ToK index dimensions and items were used once again to understand the relative weightage of each dimension out of 100. For this purpose, a list of assigned weightages (mentioned in sources) was prepared and then the list of weightage for the ToK index was developed. Appendix-II – provides details of dimension weightages assigned in utilized sources, whereas the summary of the final weightage per dimension and sub-dimension is as follows:

Table-6: ToK Ranking Index - Dimension and Sub-Dimension Weightage

Dimensions	Sub-Dimensions	Weightage	Total
1. Academic Activity	None	25%	25%
2. KT through Research	Academic Publication	12%	20%
	Research Projects	8%	
3. KT through Trained	Faculty	10%	15%

People	Graduates	5%	
4. KT through Accessibility	None	10%	10%
5. KT through Networking	None	10%	10%
6. KT through Technology	None	10%	10%
7. KT through Value Creation	Entrepreneurship and Innovation	7%	10%
	Community Programs	3%	
Total		100%	

KT through Academic Activity being the primary or core activity of an HEI is given the highest weightage i.e. 25% (out of 100%) compared to the other dimensions (the same can be observed in the shortlisted sources). KT through Research follows academic activity with 20% (out of 100%) weightage. Since KT through research is divided into two dimensions therefore the overall 20% weightage of research is further divided into two. Academic publications carry a higher weightage in HEIs partially because it is not only used as an index of measuring the faculty's performance but is also used to gauge the overall performance of the HEI as well. Similarly, research publication is considered as THE output of an HEI along with the academic activity. Thus, 12% is assigned to research publications and 8% to research projects. The assignment of weightage was strictly aligned with the shortlisted sources. The problem of weightage assignment for the last four dimensions was challenging as they are the least studied (quantifiable terms) dimensions. Though entrepreneurship and innovation are discussed in almost all the mentioned sources, discussion on networking, accessibility, and technology is scattered. Hence, 10% each was assigned to each category, assuming equal importance, but relatively less than the three major components i.e. academic activity, research activity and capacity of trained people (faculty and graduates).

Once the dimensions and sub-dimensions weights were assigned (based on mentioned sources), weightage per item within a dimension or sub-dimension was assigned in the next step. The guiding principles remained to be the same literature sources. The following tables show the weightage of items in KT through Academic Activity dimensions. KT through Academic Activity overall weightage out of 100 is 25%. This 25% was divided into 05 items as follows:

Table-7: KT through Academic Activity – Item-wise Weightage

KT through Academic Activity-25%		
Dimensions	Items	Weightage %
KT through Academic Activity	AA1	30
	AA2	25
	AA3	20
	AA4	15
	AA5	10
Total		100%

Academic activity one i.e. The total number of taught degree programs in an HEI was assigned 30%, academic activity2 i.e. Number of new degree programs since 2015 was given 25% and so on. As stated earlier these scores are in line with the score assignment of ORICs scorecard (2018), HEC ranking criteria (2013-2014) and QS star methodology (2013-18). An additional source, FRMAI Scoring Methodology (2015) was also adapted in weights assignment to dimensions and its subsequent division within each dimension. **Measurement Score Development**

The following step-wise process was followed for measurement score development:

Figure-4: Measurement Score Development Steps

Scoring criteria for 86 items were developed based on the aforementioned source (excluding the FRMAI-methodology, as it was used for weights and score assignment and its subsequent calculations). The scoring criteria for the first dimension i.e. Academic activity is explained below

Table-8: Scoring Criteria for Academic Activity

KT through Academic Activity-25%			
Dimensions	Items	Weightage %	Scoring Criteria
Academic Activity	AA1	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 5 (1-10% of total no. of departments) ● 10 (10% and above)
	AA2	25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 5 (1-10% of total no. of departments) ● 10 (10% and above)
	AA3	20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 5 (once a year) ● 10 (more than once a year)
	AA4	15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 5 (1-10% of total no. of departments) ● 10 (10% and above)
	AA5	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 5 (1-10% of total no. of departments) ● 10 (10% and above)
Total		100%	

For contextualization, the scoring criteria mentioned in QS star methodology was lowered e.g. if QS star methodology has taken 40% as minimum score value it was taken as 10% in the index, the lower score criteria helped localize the measurement and also helped in aligning it with HEC ORIC scorecard (2018) scoring criteria. The HEIs received responses were standardized by applying the scoring criteria. The standardized scores were divided into two categories only i-e 5 (minimum score) and 10 (maximum score). HEC-Performance Matrices for ORIC (2018) has used a standardized score of 2 (minimum score) and 4 (maximum score).

If an HEI score on academic activity one (AA1) was within the range of 1% to 10% of the number of departments it was given a score of 05, in case the score was higher than the given range the HEI was given a 10 score in AA1. The same is explained with help of HEI-I scores as follows:

Table-9: Scoring Calculation

Items	HEI Response *	Scoring Criteria	Calculation	Standard Score
AA1	101	5 (1-10% of total no. of departments); 10 (10% and above)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Total Departments = 31, ● 10% of 31 = $31 * 0.1 = 3.1$ The received responses of AA1 and AA4 are above 3.1, thus the standardized score of these items is 10 respectively	10
AA2	0	5 (1-10% of total no. of departments); 10 (10% and above)		0
AA3	0	5 (once a year); 10 (more than once a year)		0
AA4	4	5 (1-10% of total no. of departments); 10 (10% and above)		10
AA5	0	5 (1-10% of total no. of departments); 10 (10% and above)		0

The scoring criteria were applied to all 86 items and standard scores were determined. It should be clear that the scoring criteria varies and is not the same across all 86 items. Once the standard score was determined the assigned weightage per item, sub-dimension and dimension came into play. The following table shows sample calculations of weightage application.

Table-10: Academic Activity Score Determination

Academic Activity (25%)						
	Standard Score	Max. Score	Assigned Score %	% Score Calculation	% Score	Academic Activity Score (25% weightage)
AA1	10	10	30	$10/10 * 30$	30	$45/100 * 25 = 11.25\%$
AA2	0	10	25	$0/10 * 25$	0	
AA3	0	10	20	$0/10 * 20$	0	
AA4	10	10	15	$10/10 * 15$	15	
AA5	0	10	10	$0/10 * 10$	0	

* Hypothetical response from an HEI

	100%		45%	
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Based on a hypothetical response from an HEI, it is determined that the HEI (hypothetical) in point has an overall score of 11.25% on the first dimension i-e KT through Academic Activity. This percentage now requires an interpretation in terms of Low, High, or Medium transfer of knowledge.

2.3.1. Categorization of HEI

The categorization of calculated scores was rooted in learnings from FRMAI Scoring Methodology (2015) and HEC-Pakistan Performance Matrices for ORIC (2018). Reviewing both the methodologies, the following categorization for the ToK index was developed:

Table-11: Transfer of Knowledge Ranking Index- Ranking Categories

Percentage Score Range	Interpretation
1%-49%	Low Transfer of Knowledge
50%-74%	Medium Transfer of Knowledge
75%-100%	High Transfer of Knowledge

Thus, applying the ranking categorization to the hypothetical calculation, it is interpreted that the HEI is in the low transfer of knowledge category on its academic activity (a score of 45% out of 100%).

2.4. Content Validation of Index

Once the index was developed, it was shared with Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP)-ORICs coordinating office. During the time frame during which the index was shared with KP-ORICs, all KP-ORICs were working on developing performance measurement matrices for HEI, a task assigned by HEC. HEC and ORICs were jointly working on developing a performance measurement that was aligned with the HEC mission of knowledge-based economy vision. Thus, a meeting with KP-ORICs was arranged whereby the transfer of knowledge index was shared. Following feedback was received:

- i. The ToK index was aligned with the mission of establishing ORICs by HEC
- ii. ORICs were collecting data on some items given in the ToK index.
- iii. Few items were new to ORICs but they agreed that the items were essential for transfer activity e.g. research papers citation data and number of students who presented in national or international conferences.
- iv. During the meeting, it was pointed out that a few of the items data was collected by Quality Enhancement Cells (QEC) of HEIs e.g. items in academic activity, faculty development, and access.
- v. Similarly, data of items related to graduates placement was looked after by career development centers (CDC) of HEI.

Thus as a result of the meetings with ORICs, the index was shared with QEC and operational CDC of an HEI. In the content validation stage, the emphasis was on the content of the index. It was considered necessary to ensure that the HEI were familiar with the content and had dealt with this kind of data directly.

After meetings with ORICs, QEC, and Planning and Development sections of HEI, the index was finalized with minor changes in jargons. As the last step of instrument development, the ToK index was pilot tested.

2.5. Pilot Testing

Pilot testing was comparatively easy as the HEI already were aware of such indices in the form of ORIC scorecard and HEC ranking criteria. The study reviewed the work of Dillman, (2000), Hinkin, (2009) and Lazar, Feng, Hochheiser (2010). Based on the mentioned sources following pilot testing process was designed for the study:

Figure-5 ToK Pilot Test Process

(Adapted from Dillman (2000), Hinkin (2009), and Lazar et al. (2010))

Pilot testing was conducted following four steps. In the planning phase, a detailed plan was prepared that included the development of a worksheet to be used for recording the duration of the data collection, comments/reservations/remarks and the calculations related challenges.

Once it was documented what to record as feedback of the pilot test, the second stage of selecting a pilot sample was initiated. One HEI on a convenience basis was selected. The sampled HEI was contacted in person and were briefed about the survey and pilot test. Upon agreement, an email was sent to the concerned person. The

email described the objectives of the study, the purpose of data collection, voluntary participation and confidentiality of data. The ToK ranking index was attached in pdf format.

The date, pseudonym of sampled HEI, mode of sharing, and ORIC office name was noted in the worksheet prepared for pilot testing. During the data collection process, the questions listed in the worksheet were filled in as and when the feedback was received. Following feedback was received after the completion of the pilot test:

- i. Four weeks were taken by the concerned offices to return the filled in ToK index.
- ii. After the email, the concerned office requested an additional hard copy and a cover letter duly signed.
- iii. During the data collection, the concerned office informed that data regarding the number of enrolled and graduated students are recorded by the academic/registrar office, data related to the number of students involved in experiential learnings and placement is recorded by career development centers and data related to academic programs by quality enhancement cells. Thus, phone calls and visits were arranged to the mentioned offices.
- iv. Data on several items of KT through networking and KT through graduates was not collected by the sampled HEI.
- v. Terms like venture capital, seed capital needed additional description.
- vi. A distinction in contractual research and collaborative research was also reported to be confusing for the staff of the concerned office, though they were directly taken from the ORIC scorecard (2018). The office shared that it was easy to understand the required data on contractual and collaborative research via the signing of MOU with institutions as a referral.
- vii. General comments included: familiarity of items in the ToK index, lack of current data, and centralized data center and lack of staff in ORIC because of which the data collection took more than a month.

The aforementioned points were revisited and were incorporated in the ToK index and data collection process. Following is the list of revisions:

- i. Four (04) to eight (08) weeks was decided as data collection duration if the data was to be collected from HEI manually.
- ii. It was decided to carry on with the items in KT through networking and KT through people, in case all the sampled HEI did not respond on the mentioned items then it would be removed at the time of analysis. The decision was based on assessing the kind of data HEI collect about networking, graduates and faculty.
- iii. Venture capital and seed capital were defined in the footnotes of the ToK index shared with HEI.
- iv. The research project items were rewritten as follows:

Table-12: Revision after Pilot Test

Before Pilot Test	After Pilot Test
i. Number of contractual research with public funding	i. Number of research projects with HEC funding (e.g. NRPU, SRGP)
ii. Number of industry-sponsored research projects at HEI	ii. Number of research projects with Govt. funding (provincial and Federal)
iii. Number of international development partner (world bank, USAID, UNDP, etc) sponsored research projects at HEI	iii. Number of Research projects with Industry funding (National)
	iv. Number of Research Projects with International development partners funding (UNDP, USAID, World Bank, etc.)

Weights and scores for the items were readjusted. The overall weightage of 20% to KT through research and 8% to research projects was kept the same.

Once the pilot data was collected (hard form) from the sampled HEI, it was initially recorded in MS-Excel for data cleaning purposes. Two sheets were prepared, one with a complete ToK index and the other with no data on items related to KT through networking and KT through people (graduates). This step was taken to calculate the impact on overall scoring and the final ranking. The filled-in original data was then scored as per the scoring criteria. The scores were then converted into SPSS-22. The calculation process explained in table-11 was followed and scores of the pilot test were calculated. The same process was repeated by removing no data items. The following table shows the scores of pilot HEI with and without no data items.

Table-13: Pilot Test Results of Un-Omitted Items

KT Dimensions	Out of Respective Dimension %age	Out of 100% per Dimension	ToK Categorization
KT Through Academic Activity (25%)	10%	40%	Low Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Research (20%)	17%	85%	High Transfer of Knowledge

KT Through Trained People (15%)	9%	60%	Medium Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Access (10%)	8%	80%	High Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Network (10%)	5%	50%	Medium Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Technology (10%)	1%	10%	Low Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Value Creation (10%)	5%	50%	Medium Transfer of Knowledge
Overall ToK Ranking Percentage And Interpretation	55%	Medium Transfer of Knowledge	

Table-14: Pilot Test Results of Omitted Items

KT Dimensions	Out of Respective Dimension %age	Out of 100% per Dimension	ToK Categorization
KT Through Academic Activity (25%)	10%	40%	Low Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Research (20%)	17%	85%	High Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Trained People (15%)	14%	93%	Medium Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Access (10%)	8%	80%	High Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Network (10%)	6%	60%	Medium Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Technology (10%)	1%	10%	Low Transfer of Knowledge
KT Through Value Creation (10%)	5%	50%	Medium Transfer of Knowledge
Overall ToK Ranking Percentage And Interpretation	61%	Medium Transfer of Knowledge	

The sampled pilot HEI transfer's 10% of the total 54% transferred knowledge via academic activity i-e. Through degree programs, diploma courses, and associate degree programs, 17% through research i-e research publications and research projects, 9% through trained people i-e. Through faculty and graduates. This score is different when the items with no data were removed, the score improved by 5%. 8% of the transfer is through access, 5% through the network, again when items with no data were removed the score improved by 1%. The pilot HEI transfer only 0.88% of the total 54% via technology and 5% via value creation.

Both the final scores 54% (with no data items) and 60% (without data items) are in the range of medium transfer of knowledge category. Thus. There is a difference if dimension-wise scored but the overall ranking of the sampled HEI remained the same. Regardless of no effect on the overall ranking, it was decided to share the complete 86 items ToK with KP-HEI and calculate two scores as done for the pilot HEI.

2.5.1. Summary of Pilot Test

No major problem regarding the understanding of the ToK index was faced during the pilot testing. The reason behind the smooth operation was mainly because the ToK index was adapted from literature and ORIC was familiar with such data collection instruments e.g. ORIC scorecard. Furthermore, the index required secondary data therefore, it was easy for the ORIC office to report the data that they have already collected either for annual reports, ranking or for ORIC scorecard.

Part-II: The Automation of Transfer of Knowledge Ranking Index

Given the unprecedented benefits of automation ranging from cost efficiency to paperless environment to ready availability of data etc., it was decided to develop an automated version of the Transfer of Knowledge Index. Updated OpenSource technology was used in development by keeping security and performance in vies. Since the aim was to make the data accessible to all users (HEIs and Higher education department) therefore data accessibility was prioritized. Figure 6 provides details of the technologies used and data accessibility protocols.

Figure-7: Data Accessibility and Technology used in automating ToK Index

The following figure describes the architecture of the developed automated version of the ToK index.

Figure-8 Architecture

Two types of user interfaces were developed: university user account and administration user account, in this case, the admin account was developed for higher education commission and higher education development. University users are responsible for the creation of university profiles, uploading of University data for ranking, feedback on form submission, university profile creation is one time once the profile is created the user can update any time. Whereas, the admin user is responsible for approval of university profile once the profile is approved the university user can upload the data also the admin user can generate different types of reports based on data provided by university user, the ranking of university and also can give reply to feedback submitted by university user.

The Final Word

The study aimed to develop a ranking index that not only is aligned with the expected role of HEIs in the new knowledge economy paradigm but is also consistent with the reason for the existence of HEIs i-e creation and transfer of knowledge. Given, the virtual existences and benefits of ICT interventions the newly developed ranking index provides an edge to users (HEIs) and policy regulators on the automation grounds. The study suggests that the implementation of the ToK ranking index will not only assist in measuring the performance of HEIs regarding Knowledge management (KM) activities but will also assist in understanding the conceptual ambiguities related to the transfer of knowledge in HEIs. Furthermore, the implementation of the ToK ranking index will trigger the much-needed debate of defining and measuring the entire KM process i-e creation, transfer, storage and re-application of knowledge.

Author's Contribution

The shared article is one of the output of Shabana Gul's (principle author) PhD thesis titled "The role of organizational culture in transfer of knowledge: a case of higher education institutions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa" supervised by Dr. Waseef Jamal (co-author of the article). The work is an original piece conceived and developed by Shabana Gul for her PhD and is supervised by Dr. Jamal. The authors acknowledge the contribution of their colleagues, Mr. Naveed Ahmad, Assistant Professor at University of Peshawar and Dr. Attah-Ur-Rehman, Associate Professor at Institute of Management Sciences, Peshawar for guidance and review.

References

- Anowar, F., Helal, M. A., Afroj, S., Sultana, S., Sarker, F. & Mamun, K. A. (2015). *A Critical Review on World University Ranking in Terms of Top Four Ranking Systems. New Trends in Networking, Computing, E-learning, Systems Sciences, and Engineering*, 559-566 Springer, Cham.
- Argote, L. & Ingram P. (2000). Knowledge transfer, A basis for competitive advantage in firms. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 82(1), 150-169.
- AUTM, U. (2010). Licensing Activity Survey FY 2006. *Association of University Technology*.
- Babbie, E. (2012). *The practice of research*. Belmont, Woodsworth.
- Bostrom, D., & Flanigan, S. (2003). Association of University Technology Managers Licensing Survey. *Technology 32*, 2003-2004.
- Cha, H. S., Pingry, D. E., & Thatcher, M. E. (2008). Managing the knowledge supply chain: An Organizational Learning Model Of Information Technology Offshore Outsourcing. *MIS Quarterly*, 281-306.
- Crossman, A. (2019). *Deviance and Strain Theory in Sociology*. Retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com/structural-straintheory-3026632>.
- DeVellis, R. (2012). *Scale Development, Theory and Applications*. Thousand Oaks, CA Sage.
- Dillman, D. A. (2000). *Mail and web-based survey, the tailored design method*. NY, John Wiley & Sons.
- Dunning, J. H. (2000). The eclectic paradigm as an envelope for economic and business theories of MNE activity. *International business review 9*(2), 163-190.
- Gerhardt, T. (2019). An analysis of the impact of a leadership intervention on an undergraduate work-based learning project for human resource management students. *Journal of Work-Applied Management*.
- Hansen, M. T. (1999). The search-transfer problem: The role of weak ties in sharing knowledge across organization subunits. *Administrative science quarterly*, 44(1), 82-111.
- Hinkin, T. R. (2009). *Research in Organizations c. 21*, Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Holi, M. T. & Wickramasinghe, R. (2008). *Metrics for the evaluation of knowledge transfer activities at universities*. Cambridge, Library House 5.
- Kang, J., Rhee, M., & Kang, K. H. (2010). Revisiting knowledge transfer, Effects of knowledge characteristics on organizational effort for knowledge transfer. *Expert systems with applications 37*(12), 8155-8160.
- Kwan, M. M., & Cheung, P. K. (2006). The knowledge transfer process: From field studies to technology development. *Journal of Database Management (JDM)*, 17(1), 16-32.
- Lazar, J., Feng, J. H. & Hochheiser, H. (2010). Automated Data Collection Methods. *Research Methods in Human-Computer Interaction*, 308-341.
- Levine, A. (2006). Will universities maintain control of teacher education? Change, *The Magazine of Higher Learning 38*(4), 36-43.
- Li, C. Y., & Hsieh, C. T. (2009). The impact of knowledge stickiness on knowledge transfer implementation, internalization, and satisfaction for multinational corporations. *International Journal of Information Management*, 29(6), 425-435.
- Lichtenthaler, U. (2010). Outward knowledge transfer: the impact of project-based organization on performance. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 19(6), 1705-1739.
- Mahmood, K. (2016). *Overall Assessment of the Higher Education Sector*. Higher Education Commission (HEC), H-9, Islamabad, Pakistan, 1-80.
- Martinkenaite, I. (2011). Antecedents and consequences of inter-organizational knowledge transfer. *Baltic Journal of Management*.

- Moed, H. F. (2017). A critical comparative analysis of five world university rankings. *Scientometrics* 110(2), 967-990.
- Nonaka, I. & Takeuchi H. (1995). *The knowledge-creating company, How Japanese companies create the dynamics of innovation*, Oxford university press.
- OECD, E. (2008). JRC-EC, ". *Handbook on Constructing Composite Indicators: Methodology and User Guide*", Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
- Pérez-Nordtvedt, L., Kedia, B. L., Datta, D. K., & Rasheed, A. A. (2008). Effectiveness and efficiency of cross-border knowledge transfer: An empirical examination. *Journal of management Studies*, 45(4), 714-744.
- Powell, W. W. & Snellman K. (2004). The knowledge economy. *Annual Review of Sociology* 30, 199-220.
- Reichenfeld, L. (2011). The Barriers to Academic Engagement with Enterprise, A Social Scientist's Perspective. *Innovation through Knowledge Transfer 2010*. Vol (9), 163-176. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Spector, P. E. (1992). *Summated rating scale construction, An introduction*, Sage Publications.
- Szulanski, G. (2000). The process of knowledge transfer: A diachronic analysis of stickiness. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 82(1), 9-27.
- Vernon, M. M., Balas, E. A. & Momani, S. (2018). Are university rankings useful to improve research? A systematic review. *PLoS one* 13(3), e0193762.
- Wedgewood, M. (2006). *Mainstreaming the third stream. Beyond mass higher education, Building on experience*. Open University Press, Stony Stratford 134-157.

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